

Novel nonwood fiber sources to offset forest degradation and contribute to environmental preservation[†]

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This paper discusses the global use of nonwood fibers in the pulp and paper industry, focusing on research carried out at the Faculty of Forestry, University of Toronto. The use of nonwood fiber can reduce the global demand on forests, which will contribute to ecosystem health and preserve the heritage of this resource. Growing nonwoods as a cash crop will also contribute to the economy of local farmers. The morphology and chemistry of nonwoods in relation to pulp and paper properties are discussed in detail, with particular attention given to the chemistry of nonwood lignin and extractives in comparison to wood.

Nonwood fibers are the world's oldest source of raw material for papermaking processes. In fact, until the 1940's, straw was a major component of the U.S. fiber supply¹. In many countries, including India and China, nonwood fibers remain an important fraction of the overall fiber supply. As our global forest resource is put under increasing pressure as a fiber source in years to come, nonwood fibers may again become a dominant resource for the pulp and paper industry. It has been predicted that in the year 2000, 8.3% of the world's pulp and paper capacity will be composed of nonwood fibers². However, there is tremendous potential to increase this figure.

Nonwood fibers are ideal in locations where no trees are available for fiber, or in agricultural communities where additional revenue can be generated by the sale of the material to mills. However, very little exploratory work has been done to reveal the unique chemistry of each nonwood fiber source. In order that modern papermaking processes to be optimized, the precise chemical structure of these nonwood plants should be considered. This paper will explore the unique chemistry of commonly used nonwood fibers, including agricultural residues such as wheat and rice straws and corn stalks, bagasse, and a few more specialized plants such as kenaf and hemp.

Nonwood fibers can be differentiated into three major groups, following the example set by Atchison and McGovern¹. The current use of these groups of fibers is shown in Table 1.

The nature of nonwood fibers has meant that measuring the actual supply of nonwoods is very difficult. It has been estimated that the total availability of nonwood fibers around the world is close to 2.5 billion metric tons per annum^{2–4}. However, most of this supply is not being capitalized upon

by the industry, with the current papermaking capacity for nonwood fiber being less than 1% of the total possible supply. Currently most of the world's production of nonwood papers can be found in the Asia-Pacific region of the world,

Table 1. Current distribution of nonwood fiber use*

Nonwood group	% Nonwoods used for pulping	% Global pulp capacity
Agricultural waste		
Wheat and rice straw, bagasse, sorghum	93.1	4.8
Naturally-occurring species		
Bamboo, esparto, various grasses	2.52	0.2
Cash crops for textiles		
Kenaf, hemp, flax, cotton	4.5	3.3
Total	100	8.3

*Refs. 1 and 2.

with China and India accounting for almost 80% of total production (Table 2). These countries, having depleted a large portion of their forest resources, must now explore alternative fiber sources while preserving any forest that remains, which has greatly contributed to the popularity of nonwoods. As demand for paper and pulp products increases within these regions, the overall need for a sustainable fiber supply will become acute, and nonwood fibers will likely be better utilized.

Morphology and chemistry of nonwood fibers

A great deal is already known about the morphology and chemistry of nonwood fibers. Table 3 provides an overview of the morphology of major nonwood fibers. Within the broad category of nonwood plants, fiber morphology varies greatly. Generally, fiber grown specifically for the tex-

[†]Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

Table 2. Top 10 producers of nonwood fibers, 1993-1998*

Country	1993		1998 (Estimated)		% of Global	
	Nonwood pulping capacity (000 MT)	% of National pulping capacity	Nonwood pulping capacity (000 MT)	% of National pulping capacity	Nonwood pulping capacity	
					1993	1998
China	15246	86.9	16830	84.3	73.5	71.7
India	1307	55.5	2001	61.3	6.3	8.5
Pakistan	415	100.0	415	100.0	2.0	1.8
Mexico	321	29.2	324	29.3	1.6	1.4
Peru	298	95.2	296	95.2	1.4	1.3
Indonesia	267	22.1	267	10.1	1.3	1.1
Colombia	218	45.1	218	37.2	1.1	0.9
Thailand	209	100.0	509	100.0	1.0	2.2
Brazil	196	3.1	238	3.3	1.0	1.0
Venezuela	185	75.2	187	75.4	0.9	0.8
Total	18662	-	21285	-	90.1	90.7

*Ref. 3.

Table 3. Morphology of nonwood fibers*

Species	Length (mm)			Diameter (μm)			Aspect Ratio (length : width)
	Max.	Min.	Average	Max.	Min.	Average	
Wheat straw	3.1	0.7	1.5	27	7	14	105
Rice straw	3.5	0.6	1.5	14	5	9	170
Esparto	1.6	0.5	1.1	14	7	9	120
Bamboo	4.4	1.5	2.7	27	7	14	190
Bagasse	2.8	0.8	1.7	34	10	20	85
Cornstalks	2.9	0.5	1.5	24	14	18	85
Kenaf							
(a) bast			2.6			20	130
(b) core			0.6			30	20
Hemp							
(a) bast	31	21	25	50	30	40	625
(b) core	0.9	0.5	0.8	50	20	40	20
Jack pine			3.0			40	75
Aspen			1.0			26	40

*Refs. 6 and 7.

tiles industry is characterized by the presence of two distinctive fibrous zones. The outer or bast layer of fibers is found to be between 20 and 30 mm in length, while the inner or core of fibers averages 0.8 mm in length⁵. Naturally occurring plants, such as bamboo or esparto, have fiber lengths between 1.5 and 4 mm. Agricultural residues such as straw and bagasse measure between 0.3 and 2.0 mm in length⁶. It may be noted that the aspect ratios of nonwood fibers (i.e. the length : width ratio) are very large, more so than hardwood or softwood fibers of comparative length. This has strong implications for papermaking.

Chemically, the primary differences between woody and nonwood fibers are found in the hemicellulose, lignin, and extractable chemical components of the material. Of these differences, perhaps the most important from a papermaking point of view is that there is a good deal more silica found within nonwood plants than that found in wood. In particular, this is a characteristic that typifies agricultural residues. The hemicellulose of nonwood plant fibers tends to be extremely high in pentosans, in comparison to wood⁸. The exact structure and components of nonwood lignins are not yet fully understood, although initial studies show that

there is significant variety between different nonwood types and species. Table 4 provides an overview of the basic chemistry of the different nonwoods.

Application of nonwood fibers in the pulp and paper industry

Softwood fibers, the most commonly used fiber source for papermaking, are typically between 3 and 4 mm in length with an aspect ratio between 10 and 150. There is currently more and more interest in hardwood fibers, which range between 0.45 and 1.8 mm with aspect ratios between 43 and 45 (Ref. 9). While many nonwood fibers are comparable in length to hardwoods, the aspect ratio associated

nonwoods. Certainly, the best fibers of hemp, kenaf, cotton, and flax are in great demand by the textile industry and as such would probably only be used in speciality grades of paper; cigarette paper, currency and security, and the higher grades of writing paper. In many cases, the bast fibers are so long that additional processing is required before pulping. The core fibers of these plants are not as valuable to the textile industry, however, and could be incorporated in a variety of products, including lower-grade writing paper, linerboard, and corrugating medium. The short fibers available from agricultural residues could also be incorporated in similar products¹².

Table 4. Chemistry of nonwood fibers*

Species	Cellulose %	Lignin %	Hemicellulos e %	Ash %	Silica %
Wheat straw	50–52	16–20	26–30	5–10	4–8
Rice straw	42–46	12–15	24–30	15–20	10–18
Bamboo	7–65	24–27	17–18	3–4	1–2
Bagasse					
(a) whole	53–56	19–24	27–32	2–5	2–4
(b) depitched	56–62	19–22	31–32	2–3	1–2
Cornstalks					
Kenaf					
(a) whole	44–56	13–16	18–32	4–5	2–3
(b) bast	2–51	7–12	16–30	5–6	2–3
(c) core	33–35	17–18	19–37	3–4	1–3
Hemp					
(a) whole	43	15	34	3	
(b) bast	61	10	23	2	
(c) core	34	21	38	1	
Jack pine	41.6	28.6	29.2	0.2	<0.05
Aspen (polar)	49.0	20.9	29.4	6	

*Refs. 7, 9–11.

with these fibers is typically much higher, in the range 80–200 (Ref. 7). Some fibers, particularly bast fibers from textile plants like kenaf and hemp, are much too long for effective papermaking. Ultimately, this will greatly affect the pulping characteristics of the material. Of particular concern is slow drainage in the paper machine due to the presence of small fibers and fines, which affects potential machine speeds and ultimately the capacity¹². This also greatly affects strength properties of the material in pulp and paper products¹³. Paper made from these materials tends to be weaker in both tear and fold tests; however, the short fibers and presence of fines can improve surface quality and reduce opacity in the sheet⁸.

This great variety of fiber lengths has a profound impact on the paper grades that can be produced from different

Of the more specialized textile plants, one is particularly well suited for pulp and paper industry. It has been recognized that kenaf may be a highly valuable source of fiber for the entire industry³. Pande *et al.*¹³ found that the bast fibers of kenaf are similar in pulping behaviour to softwood species, while the core fibers are quite similar to hardwood species. Of all the more specialized nonwood plants used in the pulp and paper industry, kenaf has the shortest bast fibers, which reduces the amount of pre-processing necessary to use this fiber.

Because kenaf is not residue, but rather a dedicated cash crop, it has been proposed that farmers enter into contracts with the mill that they supply¹⁴. This ensures a steady supply of the material for the mill, and less uncertainty for the

farmer. However, maintaining a steady supply between harvests may be troublesome, especially at the northern ranges of this material. Many cultivars are available of this plant for commercial applications; it has been shown that there is actually very little difference in fiber quality across the range of kenaf planting¹⁵. However, in some regions, agricultural residues may be more attractive in terms of cost and availability for mill operations.

The pulping method employed will also have a great impact on the range of products that can be produced. Mechanical pulping is currently the principle means of pulping nonwoods. This process utilizes physical grinding plates to separate fibers from one another. This type of pulping gives an extraordinarily high yield, due to the fact that very little material is being removed during the process. Typically, yields from this process approach 95% of the total raw material mass. Today, the principle means of mechanical pulping is refiner-mechanical pulp (RMP), which retains a higher fraction of long fibers over older groundwood methods¹⁶. This process can be used in conjunction with heat (thermo-mechanical pulp or TMP), chemical pretreatment (chemi-mechanical pulp or CMP), or both (chemi-thermo-mechanical pulp or CTMP).

Mechanical pulping is particularly widely used with agricultural residues. In order to produce printable grades of paper, some bleaching must be carried out. Mohta *et al.*¹⁷ examined the feasibility of utilizing environmentally friendly bleaching processes on mechanically produced bagasse fibers. It was found that oxygen delignification and DED bleaching could be combined to reduce the environmental load by 90% over traditional bleaching techniques, in terms of color and COD measurements.

In the chemical pulping process, a chemical solution is used to break down lignin, releasing cellulosic fibers for papermaking. There are two primary chemical pulping processes: the alkaline, or Kraft process, and the acid or sulphite process. Most development in chemical pulping today concentrates upon the Kraft process, due to the excellent chemical recovery capabilities associated with this method. The Kraft pulping process is developed from the soda pulping process, which uses only NaOH as a pulping agent. Much preliminary laboratory work uses soda pulping to determine the feasibility of different temperatures and resident times. The structure of nonwood lignin is of key importance when optimizing chemical pulping processes. The three primary structures found in lignin, the coumaryl, guaiacyl, and syringyl groups are shown in Fig. 1¹⁸.

Most woody lignin has examples of coumaryl and guaiacyl groups within their lignin structure. However,

syringyl groups are normally found only in hardwoods. These groups form to create a very large and complex amorphous polymer that lacks a specific structure. The differences between hardwood and softwood lignin change the pulping characteristics of their fibers, with different species being easier to pulp than other. As there are significant differences between softwood and hardwood lignin structures, it is reasonable to assume that there will be similar differences between various nonwoods, although it is probable that the overall structure of lignin within nonwoods is less complex. Some inferences can be drawn from ongoing research.

Fig. 1

The greatest success with Kraft or soda pulping has been associated with nonwoods grown for the textile industry. Significant work has been carried out at the University of Toronto examining the delignification kinetics of kenaf and hemp. From these studies, some insight can be made into the nature of the lignin in these species.

Ralph *et al.*¹⁹ reported a high concentration of syringyl groups in the lignin of kenaf, a characteristic that reflects the chemistry of hardwood trees. These results are supported by Pande²⁰, who found kenaf to be an easily pulped material with very little redeposition of lignin on fibers during the chemical pulping process. Redeposition of lignin on cellulosic fibers, due to chemical condensation during the later stages of the soda or Kraft process, is a problem that hinders the effectiveness of pulping and reduces the quality of the pulp obtained. Condensation occurs when lignin entities, having been cleaved during the pulping process, recombine into copolymers that then condense onto the fibers within the digester. Sjöström reports that the C-5 position of the phenolic ring is the site of major reactions during the condensation process. An example of this is given in Fig. 2¹⁸. In the syringyl structure, the C5 site is occupied, which prevents a significant portion of chemical condensation.

Alkali charge for soda or Kraft pulps is in the range 12–14% for softwoods and 8–10% for hardwoods. In experimental work, charges of up to 15% active alkali have been used for hemp and kenaf^{9,20}. Residence times vary but normally are around 120 min, which is close to modern chemi-

cal pulp process residence time¹⁷. In tests carried out by Pande²⁰, it was reported that the activation energy or energy required to initiate pulping for the three kenaf fractions tested (bast, core, and whole) is less than the comparable activation energy for softwoods. Reported values of 68 kJ/g-mol for bast fibers, 91 kJ/g-mol for core fibers, and 75 kJ/g-mol

Fig. 2

for whole stem pulping are much lower than the published values of 143 kJ/g-mol for loblolly pine and 130 kJ/g-mol for western hemlock. This is a further indication that it is easier to pulp kenaf compared to softwoods²⁰. Correia⁹ found that lignin condensation and redeposition is a problem when pulping hemp fibres. It was reported that lignin is reduced to approximately 5% of the residual mass within about 100 min. However, during the final stages of pulping, lignin content begins to rise again, due to redeposition of lignin molecules upon the fiber as described above. While these results are preliminary, an inference can be made that there is a larger proportion of guaiacyl and coumaryl groups in hemp lignin. These inferences have significant ramifications for the pulping schedule of this material, as too long a residence time within the reactor could reduce the quality of the pulp produced as well as reduce the efficiency of the operation.

When pulping nonwood fibers, one major problem is the pressure drop experienced by the fiber slurry on the paper machine. Pande *et al.*¹³ explored this issue, and found that pressure drop displayed by nonwood fibers closely resembles the curve shown by traditional wood fibers. This similarity has allowed models of pressure drop to be developed for wheat straw, rice straw, and bagasse, which will greatly facilitate their use in sophisticated paper machines currently available²¹.

The use of Kraft pulping processes with agricultural residues has been less successful. As shown in Table 4, there is a high concentration of silicates in straws and bagasse. These silicates are removed from fibers during the Kraft process, but remain as deposits at later stages in the chemical recovery process. This reduces the efficiency of chemical recovery and requires the input of additional capital to make the feed viable. In recent years this problem has been addressed.

The Thermal Depolymerization Process has been designed to remove this silica from the black liquor before being deposited on the surfaces of the reactor or recovery boiler²². The process in theory is quite effective, having been shown to remove approximately 90% of the silica within the system.

Today, new alternatives to traditional mechanical and chemical pulping are being explored. Steam explosion pulping employs an extremely high-pressure chamber (3100 kPa) to compress chips of material, and then releases the pressure to 'explode' the material into a receiving vessel²³. When this method was applied to bagasse pulping, the researchers reported a pulp with similar properties to that produced by traditional techniques. Several advantages were noted, including higher burst strength and breaking length, as well as lower shive and higher fines content, resulting in shorter and more uniform fiber length²³. Currently, similar work is being done with wheat and rice straws. It has been indicated that technological development over the last two decades has greatly increased the usability of bagasse and straws in commercial pulp and paper operations²⁴. Agricultural residues, particularly wheat straw and bagasse, have also been used in conjunction with alternative pulping methods such as steam explosion pulping.

Epilogue

This paper is a respectful submission to Professor D. Nasipuri's seventyfifth celebration. My association with Professor Nasipuri covers a span of forty years, and he always has remained my 'friend, philosopher, and guide'. The most exciting time that we shared was when he spent six months as a visiting professor in our Faculty here at the University of Toronto; he left a wonderful impression upon all of us. The article submitted is based on the research carried out in my laboratory, which stems from the research training I received from Dr. Nasipuri. I have used that knowledge and mentorship to develop new areas in the pulp and paper industry on a global basis.

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